

Analyses ran with R in Jarne et al. (Connectivity and selfing drives population genetic structure in a patchy landscape: a comparative approach of four co-occurring freshwater snail species)

The general procedures only are reported here.

##Classical R libraries were used for analysis

```
library(readxl)
library(lme4)
library(vegan)
library(seriation)
library(LEA)
```

##Estimating basic statistics and correlations between genetic or environmental variables

```
mean(Essai$Mt_AMA, na.rm = T)
sd(Essai$Mt_AMA, na.rm = T)
cor.test(var1, var2)
```

##Paired t-test comparing time periods (2001-2007 vs 2008-2015) for each environmental variable

```
t.test(var_t1, var_t2, paired=TRUE)
```

##Mantel test (1000 permutations) were run with Vegan

```
#comparing geographic (geo.dist) and genetic (gen.dist) distances
mantel(geo.dist,gen.dist)
```

##Linear models - effect of environment on genetic variables (here Fst)

```
#for each species (here dataam for Aplexa marmorata)
#Envir variables: site size, vegetation cover, site connectivity, site stability
#and density of favorable habitat (DFH)
#All variables scaled prior to analysis
Fst_lm = lm(scale(dataam$Fst) ~
scale(dataam$Size)+scale(dataam$Vegetation)+scale(dataam$Connectivity)+
scale(dataam$Stability)+scale(dataam$DFH))
summary(Fst_lm)
anova(Fst_lm)
AIC(Fst_lm)
```

##Inferring clusters based on a matrix of pairwise Fst within species (pairFst)

```
#using a seriation (seriate) approach then returned a dendrogram with hclust
ordered = seriate(pairFst, method = method)
dendrogram = hclust(pairFst)
```

###The sNMF approach was implemented using LEA (should be installed with BioCManager)

```
##The input file is dat.str => Convert to .geno format
struct2geno(input.file = './dat.str',
ploidy = 2,
FORMAT = 1,
extra.row = 1,
extra.col = 2)
```

```
## Define the maximal number of ancestral populations
K=10
## Define snmf regularization parameter (default = 10 ... better to use higher values)
a=50
## Run the analysis
# Note that repetitions is set to a much higher value (50) than suggested
#by the LEA documentation, given the variation in cross-entropy
obj.snmf = snmf("./dat.str.geno",
               project = "new",
               K = 1:K,
               ploidy = 2,
               repetitions = 50,
               entropy = T,
               alpha = a
)
# Plot cross-entropy
plot(obj.snmf, col = "blue", pch = 19, cex = 1.2)
#The optimal value of K is obtained by analyzing the cross-entropy plot
#Let's assume that K = 4 (defined for recovering the right set of results for plotting)
K_opt = 4
#The following instructions is used to get the best run for a given K
bestRun = get_best_run(obj.snmf, K_opt)
```